

On the Statistical Uncertainty of Monte Carlo–Calculated Scattering Sensitivities

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803397

ABSTRACT

Sensitivity coefficients calculated with Monte Carlo codes are widely used for nuclear data uncertainty quantification in the modeling and simulation of complex 3D reactor systems. This study systematically compares sensitivity coefficients and associated statistical uncertainties for the multiplication factor and fuel temperature reactivity across multiple Monte Carlo codes (SCALE/KENO, SCALE/Shift, MCNP, and Serpent) using simple models representing light-water reactors and advanced reactor concepts. For multiplication factor sensitivities, statistical uncertainties are generally acceptable, although scattering sensitivities show significantly larger statistical uncertainties than, for example, fission and capture reactions. Fuel temperature reactivity sensitivities show significantly larger statistical uncertainties across all reactions. Elastic scattering sensitivities are the most problematic: all Monte Carlo codes fail to resolve energy-dependent coefficients, and they produce dramatically different energy-collapsed values. Critically, the use of these sensitivity coefficients in nuclear data uncertainty propagation leads to reduced statistical uncertainties in individual uncertainty contributions. This can lead to the masking of unusable sensitivity coefficients and producing misleading uncertainty results. The findings of this study show that new or enhanced methods are needed to improve Monte Carlo elastic scattering sensitivity calculations. Additionally, this study shows the relevance of verifying sensitivity coefficients through direct perturbation calculations for individual nuclide reactions, instead of only for total cross sections as commonly done.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, sensitivity, scattering, nuclear data

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of nuclear data and their associated uncertainties for the modeling and simulation of light-water reactors (LWRs) and advanced reactors has been demonstrated across numerous institutions and studies. Most nuclear data assessments have focused on the multiplication factor, and fewer studies have examined other safety-relevant quantities, such as temperature reactivity feedback coefficients.

Due to the complexity of reactor models, nuclear data sensitivity and uncertainty analyses are typically performed using methods integrated into Monte Carlo neutron transport codes. These methods enable exact geometric representation and the use of continuous-energy (CE) cross sections. However, all Monte Carlo results are subject to statistical uncertainties, which are usually reported alongside the calculated results.

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This manuscript has been authored by UT-Battelle, LLC, under contract DE-AC05-00OR22725 with the US Department of Energy (DOE). The US government retains and the publisher, by accepting the work for publication, acknowledges that the US government retains a non-exclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, world-wide license to publish or reproduce the submitted manuscript version of this work, or allow others to do so, for US government purposes. DOE will provide public access to these results of federally sponsored research in accordance with the DOE Public Access Plan (<https://energy.gov/doe-public-access-plan>).

A previous study [1] revealed substantial statistical uncertainties in elastic scattering sensitivities for advanced reactor full-core reactivity analyses. When these sensitivities were combined with nuclear data covariance matrices, their statistical uncertainties propagated into significant uncertainties in the individual nuclide-reaction uncertainty contributions to the quantities of interest. The affected sensitivities primarily involved scattering cross sections. In severe cases, the statistical uncertainty contamination rendered the results unusable, necessitating the use of the computationally expensive random sampling approach instead.

This study systematically compares statistical uncertainties in sensitivities calculated via Monte Carlo-based methods. Sensitivities of the multiplication factor k_{inf} and fuel temperature reactivity were analyzed for small unit cell models representative for LWR and several advanced reactor concepts. Comparisons were conducted across three widely used sensitivity and uncertainty analysis tools: SCALE, MCNP, and Serpent. Direct cross section perturbation results and deterministic neutron transport code results serve as the reference for evaluating the performance of these Monte Carlo tools.

2. APPROACH

2.1. Test problems and quantities

Figure 1 shows the simple test models used in this study: reflected unit cells for a pressurized water reactor (PWR), a graphite-moderated high-temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR)¹ [2], a graphite-moderated molten salt reactor (MSR) [3], a molten chloride fast reactor (MCFR) [4], and a sodium-cooled fast reactor (SFR) [5]. The use of these models provides coverage of various materials and neutron spectra. The PWR, HTGR, and MSR models use fresh fuel; the SFR model uses beginning of cycle (uranium-transuranic) fuel. A temperature of 300 K was applied for all nominal models. The quantities examined herein are the infinite multiplication factor (eigenvalue), k_{inf} , and the fuel temperature reactivity (calculated as the reactivity difference between k_{inf} at 300 K and 600 K):

$$\Delta\rho_{T_f} = \frac{1}{k_{300\text{K}}} - \frac{1}{k_{600\text{K}}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Simple test models covering various reactor concepts.

2.2. Eigenvalue and reactivity difference sensitivity coefficients

This work examines sensitivity coefficients as obtained via first-order perturbation theory. Sensitivity coefficients, which quantify the relative change in a response resulting from a relative change in the cross section, are computed for a response of interest (e.g., k_{inf}) with respect to the input nuclear cross

¹To enable 1D deterministic code comparison, the HTGR pebble model uses homogenized fuel rather than explicitly modeled fuel particles. Fully heterogeneous calculations are included in the complete result set.

sections. The sensitivity coefficient S of a specific response Y to a cross section Σ is expressed as follows:

$$S = \frac{dY/Y}{d\Sigma/\Sigma}. \quad (2)$$

To compute sensitivities for a reactivity difference (e.g., the reactivity difference from a fuel temperature change), two sets of k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients are used: one nominal calculation (fuel temperature of 300 K) and one perturbed calculation (fuel temperature raised to 600 K). The sensitivity coefficients for the reactivity difference $\Delta\rho$ are then calculated as follows [6]:

$$S_{\Delta\rho,\Sigma} = \frac{1}{|\Delta\rho_{1\rightarrow 2}|} \left(\frac{1}{k_2} S_{k_2,\Sigma} - \frac{1}{k_1} S_{k_1,\Sigma} \right); \quad (3)$$

where k_i and $S_{k_i,\Sigma}$ are, respectively, the k_{inf} and the sensitivity coefficients of k_{inf} for state i with respect to Σ , and $\Delta\rho_{1\rightarrow 2}$ is the reactivity difference between the two states (see Eq. [1]).

2.3. Tools to calculate sensitivity coefficients

Table I provides an overview of the applied neutron transport codes, the cross section libraries, and the method for sensitivity analysis. The TSUNAMI sensitivity and uncertainty analysis sequence of the SCALE code system [7] allows the use of several neutron transport codes and sensitivity methods. For calculations using multigroup (MG) cross section libraries, TSUNAMI supports traditional adjoint methods. For these calculations, TSUNAMI can use the 1D deterministic code XSDRN or the 3D Monte Carlo code KENO-VI as the neutron transport solver. For calculations using CE cross section libraries, TSUNAMI supports the iterated fission probability (IFP) approach [8] and the CLUTCH method [9]; both methods rely on only one forward neutron transport calculation. The IFP approach is available with both KENO-VI and the Shift Monte Carlo code, whereas the CLUTCH method is only available with KENO-VI. The Serpent [10] and MCNP [11] Monte Carlo codes both calculate sensitivities with the IFP approach. The application of all these codes and methods allows for a thorough assessment of adjoint MG versus forward CE methods across different implementations.

Table I. Overview of applied tools and methods.

Neutron transport and sensitivity analysis code	Cross section library	Method
SCALE 7.0 beta/TSUNAMI/XSDRN	MG (252 groups for moderated systems, 302 groups for fast systems)	Adjoint
SCALE 7.0 beta/TSUNAMI/KENO-VI	MG (252 groups for moderated systems, 302 groups for fast systems)	Adjoint
SCALE 7.0 beta/TSUNAMI/KENO-VI	CE	CLUTCH
SCALE 7.0 beta/TSUNAMI/KENO-VI	CE	IFP
SCALE 7.0 beta/TSUNAMI/Shift	CE	IFP
Serpent 2.2.1	CE	IFP
MCNP 6.3	CE	IFP

All calculations were performed with ENDF/B-VII.1 cross section and covariance libraries. All Monte Carlo calculations were performed for 450 active and 100 inactive generations, with 100,000 neutrons per generation. For the KENO-IFP calculations, 5 latent generations were used, whereas 10 latent generations were used for all other CLUTCH and IFP calculations.

The k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients are output by the applied codes in different formats. To simplify comparisons between the results of the different codes, all obtained k_{inf} sensitivities were converted into SCALE's sensitivity data file (SDF) HDF5 format. The calculation of sensitivity coefficients for the fuel temperature reactivity $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ was performed using SCALE's TSAR utility [6] based on a nominal and a perturbed SDF.

With respect to comparisons of elastic scattering sensitivity coefficients, it must be noted that the applied codes differ in their tallying of elastic scattering with or without consideration of the thermal scattering law $S(\alpha, \beta)$ data. The following reaction identifier numbers, MT, are used with the individual codes and referred to just as elastic scattering going forward:

- SCALE: MT=2, which is elastic scattering + $S(\alpha, \beta)$
- MCNP: MT=-3, which is elastic scattering + $S(\alpha, \beta)$
- Serpent: sum of MT=2 elastic scattering and MT=1002 $S(\alpha, \beta)$

2.4. Verification through direct perturbation

To verify the obtained sensitivity coefficients, reference sensitivity coefficients were calculated through direct perturbation (DP) of cross sections. Using SCALE's Clarolplus utility, individual cross sections of individual nuclides (e.g., the fission cross section in ^{235}U) in the MG cross section library were perturbed by a user-specified perturbation factor p . Based on Eq. (2), the sensitivity coefficient of response Y can be calculated as follows:

$$S = \frac{\Sigma (Y_+ - Y_-)}{Y (\Sigma_+ - \Sigma_-)} = \frac{1}{Y} \frac{(Y_+ - Y_-)}{(\Sigma_+/\Sigma - \Sigma_-/\Sigma)} = \frac{1}{Y} \frac{(Y_+ - Y_-)}{(p_+ - p_-)} \quad (4)$$

where indices + and - indicate a perturbation above and below 1.0, respectively (for example, $p_+=1.05$ and $p_-=0.95$ for perturbations of a cross section by $\pm 5\%$). In practice, multiple perturbations (here, up to 10%) are applied, and the sensitivity coefficient is determined via linear fitting.

2.5. Propagation of cross section uncertainties to result uncertainties

SCALE's TSUNAMI-IP utility was used to propagate cross section uncertainties to uncertainties in k_{inf} and $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ by applying first-order error propagation, also known as the "sandwich formula," using the generated SDFs. Results are the relative uncertainties of k_{inf} and $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ as well as individual contributions of the covariance matrices for the different cross sections. The cross section uncertainty propagation considered the following cross sections: elastic and inelastic scattering, (n,2n), fission, (n, γ), (n,p), (n,d), (n,t), (n, ^3He), (n, α), neutron multiplicity $\bar{\nu}$, and fission spectrum χ .

3. RESULTS

3.1. Eigenvalue sensitivity coefficients

For collapsed 1-group fission sensitivities, all codes demonstrate excellent agreement (Table II). KENO-MG and KENO-CLUTCH yield the smallest statistical uncertainties, and Shift-IFP and Serpent-IFP produce errors $2\times$ to $3\times$ larger. MCNP-IFP exhibits the largest statistical uncertainties (approximately $3\times$ greater than those of Shift-IFP and Serpent-IFP). Maximum statistical uncertainties remain below 1.2% for all selected fission sensitivities. All Monte Carlo results show excellent agreement with deterministic DP results. The energy-dependent sensitivities are clearly resolved and show small statistical uncertainties (Figure 2).

For collapsed 1-group elastic scattering sensitivities (Table III), good agreement is observed among all codes except MCNP. KENO yields the smallest statistical uncertainties, followed by Shift-IFP and Serpent-IFP, which yield errors up to $6\times$ larger depending on the reaction. Compared with other codes, MCNP-IFP shows both the largest statistical uncertainties (maximum of $\sim 28\%$ for selected sensitivities) and corresponding discrepancies in the sensitivity coefficients. All Monte Carlo results again agree with DP results. In contrast, the energy-dependent sensitivities are only well-resolved for KENO-MG and KENO-CLUTCH, whereas the Shift-IFP, Serpent-IFP, and MCNP-IFP results show very large statistical variations and errors (Figure 3).

Table II. k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients for fission cross sections. The relative 1σ statistical uncertainty is provided for all Monte Carlo results.

Code	PWR/ ²³⁵ U		HTGR/ ²³⁵ U		MSR/ ²³⁵ U		MCFR/ ²³⁵ U		SFR/ ²³⁹ Pu	
	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ
DP (XSDRN)	0.2765		0.2062		0.2235		0.4347		0.4822	
XSDRN-MG	0.2752		0.2050		0.2222		0.4573		0.4880	
KENO-MG	0.2747	0.05%	0.2058	0.11%	0.2236	0.09%	0.4574	0.01%	0.4877	0.00%
KENO-CLUTCH	0.2751	0.08%	0.2049	0.11%	0.2220	0.10%	0.4571	0.03%	0.4876	0.03%
KENO-IFP	0.2751	0.12%	0.2046	0.17%	0.2222	0.09%	0.4569	0.08%	0.4874	0.07%
Shift-IFP	0.2751	0.21%	0.2054	0.39%	0.2220	0.32%	0.4573	0.11%	0.4874	0.10%
MCNP-IFP	0.2756	0.62%	0.2030	1.11%	0.2220	0.94%	0.4574	0.32%	0.4874	0.28%
Serpent-IFP	0.2760	0.22%	0.2048	0.28%	0.2212	0.25%	0.4569	0.12%	0.4870	0.11%

Table III. k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients for elastic scattering. The relative 1σ statistical uncertainty is provided for all Monte Carlo results.

Code	PWR/ ¹ H		HTGR/Graphite		MSR/Graphite		MCFR/ ³⁷ Cl		SFR/ ²³ Na	
	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ
DP (XSDRN)	0.1728		0.1478		0.1048		-0.0276		-0.0336	
XSDRN-MG	0.1723		0.1323		0.1038		-0.0269		-0.0336	
KENO-MG	0.1687	0.65%	0.1256	3.86%	0.0726	4.53%	-0.0286	2.04%	-0.0339	0.69%
KENO-CLUTCH	0.1640	0.62%	0.1635	3.04%	0.1175	3.34%	-0.0260	1.85%	-0.0337	0.61%
KENO-IFP	0.1681	0.76%	0.1515	2.33%	0.1034	2.95%	-0.0288	4.19%	-0.0346	1.70%
Shift-IFP	0.1704	1.30%	0.1474	5.79%	0.1069	6.75%	-0.0264	6.93%	-0.0321	2.74%
MCNP-IFP	0.1744	3.70%	0.1386	18.16%	0.0994	21.69%	-0.0188	28.22%	-0.0372	6.78%
Serpent-IFP	0.1557	1.42%	0.1368	3.70%	0.0954	4.95%	-0.0261	7.30%	-0.0330	3.42%

Table IV. $\Delta\rho_{Tf}$ sensitivity coefficients for (n,γ) cross sections. The relative 1σ statistical uncertainty is provided for all Monte Carlo results.

Code	PWR/ ²³⁸ U		HTGR/ ²³⁸ U		MSR/ ²³⁸ U		MCFR/ ²³⁸ U		SFR/ ²³⁹ Pu	
	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ
DP (XSDRN)	-0.6657		-0.9351		-1.2283		-0.4571		0.3233	
XSDRN-MG	-0.6326		-0.9538		-1.2352		-0.4461		0.3305	
KENO-MG	-0.6339	0.56%	-0.9640	0.40%	-1.2098	0.74%	-0.5237	0.96%	0.3366	0.61%
KENO-CLUTCH	-0.6103	0.67%	-0.9135	0.27%	-1.1744	0.53%	-0.5620	0.75%	0.3335	0.57%
KENO-IFP	-0.6257	1.40%	-0.9192	0.52%	-1.2019	1.16%	-0.6417	2.15%	0.3044	4.28%
Shift-IFP	-0.5924	2.51%	-0.9131	1.23%	-1.1798	2.42%	-0.4911	4.10%	0.3307	2.99%
MCNP-IFP	-0.5460	8.08%	-0.8981	3.39%	-0.9339	5.66%	-0.7103	8.43%	0.3240	8.67%
Serpent-IFP	-0.5918	5.20%	-0.9737	1.42%	-1.1693	2.46%	-0.7214	11.55%	0.2655	24.51%

Table V. $\Delta\rho_{Tf}$ sensitivity coefficients for elastic scattering. The relative 1σ statistical uncertainty is provided for all Monte Carlo results.

Code	PWR/ ¹ H		HTGR/Graphite		MSR/Graphite		MCFR/ ³⁷ Cl		SFR/ ²³ Na	
	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ	S	rel. 1σ
DP (XSDRN)	0.7705		0.8844		0.9703		-0.2619		-0.3415	
XSDRN-MG	0.7476		0.9442		0.9484		-0.3129		-0.3257	
KENO-MG	0.8386	17.05%	1.0209	34.19%	0.7846	102.05%	-0.3663	57.21%	-0.2904	52.22%
KENO-CLUTCH	1.4815	8.92%	0.7055	41.40%	-1.5405	57.86%	-0.3262	53.66%	-0.3869	33.92%
KENO-IFP	0.7395	22.56%	0.4233	51.25%	1.0910	72.90%	-0.2881	152.41%	0.0165	>1,000.0%
Shift-IFP	0.4924	56.43%	0.1430	359.75%	0.5306	314.33%	-0.6651	96.33%	-1.4186	38.04%
MCNP-IFP	1.0538	80.51%	-1.7497	70.84%	-0.0234	>1,000.0%	-5.4140	34.64%	1.9474	78.65%
Serpent-IFP	0.6277	52.72%	0.9714	38.38%	0.8484	122.64%	0.1491	162.12%	-1.5334	44.05%

3.2. Fuel temperature reactivity sensitivity coefficients

For collapsed 1-group (n, γ) sensitivities (Table IV), coefficients with statistical uncertainties below 5% demonstrate good agreement across codes and with DP results. KENO-MG and KENO-CLUTCH yield the smallest statistical uncertainties ($<1\%$), whereas KENO-IFP, Shift-IFP, Serpent-IFP, and MCNP exhibit larger errors that vary by system. Maximum statistical uncertainties for selected sensitivities reach $\sim 25\%$. Energy-dependent sensitivities are clearly resolved with KENO, show moderate statistical uncertainties with Shift-IFP, and exhibit large statistical fluctuations with Serpent-IFP and MCNP-IFP that render them essentially statistical noise (not displayed due to space limitation).

Figure 2. Energy-dependent k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients to the ^{239}Pu fission cross section in the SFR model. The shaded areas indicate 2σ statistical uncertainties of the Monte Carlo results.

Figure 3. Energy-dependent k_{inf} sensitivity coefficients to ^{23}Na elastic scattering in the SFR model. The shaded areas indicate 2σ statistical uncertainties of the Monte Carlo results.

For collapsed 1-group elastic scattering sensitivities (Table V), statistical uncertainties are prohibitively large for all codes and most exceed 30%. The results exhibit substantial disagreement, including sign differences between codes. The energy-dependent sensitivities show prohibitively large statistical fluctuations across all Monte Carlo codes, rendering them essentially statistical noise; this explains the observed discrepancies in the collapsed values.

3.3. Propagation of sensitivities to uncertainties

Due to space limitations, only the total output uncertainties of k_{inf} and $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ for the SFR model are shown in Table VI. The k_{inf} uncertainties agree well across codes and have small statistical uncertainties. In contrast, $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ uncertainties exhibit much larger statistical uncertainties. KENO-MG and KENO-CLUTCH agree well with XSDRN-MG (errors below 1%), whereas all other results show statistical uncertainties up to 10% and significant deviations from the deterministic reference.

Table VII lists sensitivity coefficients and uncertainty contributions obtained with Shift-IFP. The individual contributions show large relative errors consistent with the overall $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ uncertainty. More importantly, the sensitivity coefficient statistical uncertainties are significantly larger than their propagated contributions to total uncertainty. For example, the ^{56}Fe elastic scattering sensitivity has a $\sim 141\%$ statistical uncertainty, whereas its contribution to $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ uncertainty has only a $\sim 21\%$ error. This demonstrates that analyzing only total output uncertainties can mask the large statistical uncertainties in underlying sensitivity coefficients, potentially leading to incorrect conclusions.

Table VI. Percent relative uncertainty in k_{inf} and $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ for the SFR model. The absolute 1σ statistical uncertainty is provided for all Monte Carlo results.

Code	k_{inf} uncertainty [%]	$\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ uncertainty [%]
XSDRN-MG	1.294	6.564
KENO-MG	1.300 ± 0.001	6.287 ± 0.523
KENO-CLUTCH	1.286 ± 0.004	6.303 ± 0.945
KENO-IFP	1.299 ± 0.002	7.929 ± 3.066
Shift-IFP	1.303 ± 0.001	14.633 ± 3.695
MCNP-IFP	1.313 ± 0.010	38.429 ± 10.103
Serpent-IFP	1.307 ± 0.004	16.761 ± 4.931

Table VII. Sensitivity of specific nuclide reactions and contribution of the corresponding covariance matrix to the relative output uncertainty of k_{inf} and $\Delta\rho_{T_f}$ for selected reactions for the SFR model as obtained with Shift-IFP.

Reaction	k_{inf}				$\Delta\rho_{T_f}$				
	S	rel. 1σ	Contr. [%]	rel. 1σ	Reaction	S	rel. 1σ	Contr. [%]	rel. 1σ
$^{238}\text{U } n, n'$	-0.102	0.65%	1.077	0.2%	$^{238}\text{U } n, n'$	-1.4839	27.62%	10.662	14.7%
$^{239}\text{Pu } n, \gamma$	-0.050	0.03%	0.353	0.0%	^{23}Na elastic	-1.4186	38.04%	6.418	17.1%
$^{239}\text{Pu } n, n'$	-0.012	2.05%	0.339	0.2%	$^{239}\text{Pu } n, n'$	-0.2454	60.80%	6.057	16.8%
^{239}Pu fission	0.487	0.10%	0.218	0.0%	^{56}Fe elastic	0.4825	140.89%	5.616	20.8%
^{23}Na elastic	-0.032	2.74%	0.204	0.2%	^{238}U elastic	-0.2061	510.24%	3.461	41.9%
^{56}Fe elastic	-0.021	5.18%	0.168	0.3%	$^{239}\text{Pu } n, \gamma$	0.3307	2.99%	2.442	0.4%

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study compares the statistical uncertainties of sensitivity coefficients across multiple Monte Carlo codes. For eigenvalue sensitivities, uncertainties are generally small, although scattering sensitivities exhibit larger errors than, for example, capture and fission. For fuel temperature reactivity, uncertainties

increase significantly across all reactions, with some codes being unable to resolve even neutron capture sensitivities. Elastic scattering sensitivities are most problematic: All Monte Carlo codes fail to resolve energy-dependent coefficients and produce inconsistent energy group-collapsed values. Although not presented here, this is also applicable when dramatically increasing the number of simulated neutron histories. This reflects the high variance of collision-specific tallies, where infrequent collision events degrade estimator precision. In nuclear data uncertainty propagation, the large statistical uncertainty of sensitivity coefficients propagates to *reduced* statistical uncertainties in individual uncertainty contributions. This can mask unusable individual sensitivities and produce misleading uncertainty results.

These results highlight the need for improved Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis methods, including the use of variance-reduction techniques and alternative estimators, to enable reliable elastic scattering sensitivity calculations. Without such advances, meaningful uncertainty quantification of essential reactor physics parameters, such as reactivity coefficients, remains unattainable. Additionally, obtained sensitivities should always be verified through DP calculations, including sensitivities of individual reaction cross sections instead of total cross sections as commonly done.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was performed with funding from the US Department of Energy, Office of Science, Nuclear Data Program. The authors appreciate Cihangir Celik's review and the valuable discussions.

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